

SHORT COMMUNICATION

VEXAS syndrome in a nutshell

Nurul Hazliana Harun

Dr. Nurul Hazliana Harun, Lecturer, Dept. of Physiology, Faculty of Medicine, Quest International University (QIU), No. 227, Plaza Teh Teng Seng (Level 2), Jalan Raja Permaisuri Bainun, 30250 Ipoh, Perak Darul Ridzuan, Malaysia

Email: hazliana.nurul90@gmail.com [\[ORCID\]](#)

Information about the article:

Received: May 21, 2023

Accepted: June 28, 2023

Published online: July 1, 2023

Publisher

Quest International University (QIU), No.227, Plaza Teh Teng Seng (Level 2), Jalan Raja Permaisuri Bainun, 30250 Ipoh, Perak Darul Ridzuan, Malaysia

e-ISSN: 2636-9478

© The Author(s). 2023

Content licensing: [CC BY 4.0](#)

ABSTRACT

Introduction:

VEXAS is a multisystem autoinflammatory disorder caused by acquired somatic mutations in the ubiquitin-like modifier activating the X chromosome's enzyme 1 (UBA1) gene. VEXAS syndrome predominantly affects men, with the disease typically presenting with a progressive onset after age 50. Patients exhibit a wide range of clinical symptoms which involve skin, lungs, cartilage, and joints. Common systemic symptoms include recurring, unexplained fever episodes, general malaise, and fatigue. The care of VEXAS syndrome is challenging and necessitates a multidisciplinary approach from numerous specialized teams due to its heterogeneous manifestations. Although no standardised therapies are available for VEXAS patients, high-dose, long-term corticosteroid therapies and Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors are used as therapeutic options.

Conclusion:

Clinicians should consider VEXAS syndrome in patients with unexplained systemic inflammatory symptoms, particularly when accompanied by peripheral cytopenia and other hematologic disorders.

Keywords

Autoinflammatory, manifestations, patients, symptoms, syndrome, ubiquitin-like modifier activating the enzyme 1 (UBA1), vacuole

Introduction

In 2020, a rare and severe multisystem autoinflammatory disorder with complex pathogenesis was first described by scientists as VEXAS syndrome (vacuole, E1 enzyme, X-linked, autoinflammatory, and somatic). Acquired somatic mutations in the ubiquitin-like modifier activating the enzyme 1 (UBA1) gene on the X chromosome cause this syndrome. [1] UBA1 initiates the protein ubiquitylation process, a post-translational modification (PTM) targeting proteins for various vital cellular processes, including degradation, signalling, localization, and protein-protein interactions. [2]

A crucial observation of bone marrow smears from VEXAS patients is the presence of cytoplasmic vacuoles within myeloid and erythroid precursor cells [1]. They are not pathognomonic for VEXAS syndrome since they can also be observed in copper deficiency, zinc toxicity, alcoholism, or myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS). [3] However, these findings are rare, and if they are detected in the presence of inflammatory symptoms, genetic analysis is strongly recommended to investigate the possibility of VEXAS syndrome. Also, clinicians should not rule out the possibility of VEXAS syndrome without a vacuole, as certain patients may not present with vacuoles on a bone marrow smear. [4]

VEXAS syndrome predominantly affects men, with the disease typically presenting with a progressive onset occurring after age 50, though it can affect women too. A study by Beck DB *et al.* has shown that within the initial cohort of 25 male patients, the female second X-chromosome allele has a protective influence against the pernicious impact of the mutated UBA1 allele [1]. More recent studies describing the VEXAS syndrome in women with monosomy X support this hypothesis. [5, 6]

Patients with VEXAS syndrome exhibit many clinical symptoms that can impact several organ systems, such as the skin, lungs, cartilage, and joints. Common systemic symptoms include recurring, unexplained fever episodes, general malaise, and fatigue. [1, 7] The VEXAS syndrome is characterised by cutaneous involvement, which manifests as neutrophilic dermatosis and a vasculitis rash [1, 8]. According to current research, 88% of patients reported cutaneous symptoms, with a significant number of people (45%) presenting the symptoms as the initial complication. [9] People with VEXAS syndrome typically experience pulmonary involvement, with the most common manifestations being pulmonary infiltration and venous thromboembolism. [1, 10] Less frequent symptoms include interstitial pneumonia and pleural effusion. [10]. Arthritis and chondritis are frequent features of the VEXAS syndrome. [8] Cytopenia and macrocytic anaemia are frequent haematological findings. [1, 9, 11] To rule out VEXAS syndrome, genetic testing should be undertaken for people whose aetiology of these manifestations is unknown.

The care of VEXAS syndrome is challenging and necessitates a multidisciplinary approach from numerous specialized teams due to its heterogeneous manifestations. To date, there are no standardized therapies for VEXAS patients. Generally, the current treatments have two objectives: to prevent systemic inflammation and to eradicate the UBA1-mutated population of hematopoietic cells. In addition, medications for managing the multi-organ manifestations are needed. Patients often respond to high-dose, long-term corticosteroid therapies. However, the side effects after dosage tapering are frequent. [12] This highlights the need for more effective therapy for the disease.

Janus kinase (JAK) inhibitors may be a therapeutic option for VEXAS patients, targeting multiple pathways activating systemic inflammation. Among the JAK inhibitors, the JAK1 and JAK2 inhibitor ruxolitinib was more effective in VEXAS syndrome treatment. Clinical and laboratory responses have been observed in approximately 50% of patients within one month, and the response rates exceeded 80% at the three-month assessment. [13]

Conclusion

Diagnosing VEXAS syndrome can be challenging since it is newly discovered, has overlapping clinical features with other autoinflammatory disorders, and requires high-cost genetic testing. Clinicians should consider VEXAS syndrome in patients with unexplained systemic inflammatory symptoms, particularly when accompanied by peripheral cytopenia and other hematologic disorders. Since the discovery of this syndrome, much ongoing research has aimed to elucidate further the molecular mechanisms linking the UBA1 gene to VEXAS syndrome, with the idea of improving the diagnosis, management, and treatment strategies for individuals affected by this rare condition to improve their quality of life.

Abbreviations

Janus kinase inhibitor (JAK), myelodysplastic syndrome (MDS), post-translational modification (PTM), ubiquitin-like modifier activating the enzyme 1 (UBA1), vacuole, E1 enzyme, X-linked, autoinflammatory and somatic (VEXAS).

Acknowledgments

Author is grateful to Amanpreet Kaur Gurdarshan Singh of Quest International University for her contributions to the manuscript's language and grammar editing.

Funding

No funding was received.

Availability of data and materials

All data are available as part of the article, and no additional source data are required.

Competing interests

We declare no competing interests.

Publisher's Note

QIU remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations. The publisher shall not be legally responsible for any types of loss, actions, claims, proceedings, demand, or costs or damages whatsoever caused arising directly or indirectly in connection with or arising out of the use of this material.

References

1. Beck DB, Ferrada MA, Sikora KA, Ombrello AK, Collins JC, Pei W, *et al.* Somatic Mutations in UBA1 and Severe Adult-Onset Autoinflammatory Disease. *N Engl J Med.* 2020;383(27):2628-38. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2026834>
2. Callis J. The ubiquitination machinery of the ubiquitin system. *Arabidopsis Book.* 2014;12:e0174. <https://doi.org/10.1199/tab.0174>
3. Gurnari C, Pagliuca S, Durkin L, Terkawi L, Awada H, Kongkiatkamon S, *et al.* Vacuolization of hematopoietic precursors: an enigma with multiple etiologies. *Blood.* 2021;137(26):3685-89. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood.2021010811>
4. Templé M, Duroyon E, Croizier C, Rossignol J, Huet T, Friedrich C, *et al.* Atypical splice-site mutations causing VEXAS syndrome. *Rheumatology (Oxford).* 2021;60(12):e435-e437. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rheumatology/keab524>
5. Barba T, Jamilloux Y, Durel CA, Bourbon E, Mestrallet F, Sujobert P, *et al.* VEXAS syndrome in a woman. *Rheumatology (Oxford).* 2021;60(11):e402-e403. <https://doi.org/10.1093/rheumatology/keab392>
6. Luquet I, El Kassir A, Sailler L, Largeaud L, Mansat-De Mas V. Characteristic vacuolization of myeloid precursors and UBA1 mutation in a woman with monosomy X. *Int J Lab Hematol.* 2022;44(1):29-30. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijlh.13617>
7. Templé M, Kosmider O. VEXAS Syndrome: A Novelty in MDS Landscape. *Diagnostics (Basel).* 2022;12(7):1590. <https://doi.org/10.3390/diagnostics12071590>
8. Al-Hakim A, Savic S. An update on VEXAS syndrome. *Expert Rev Clin Immunol.* 2023;19(2):203-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1744666X.2023.2157262>
9. Hines AS, Mohandesi NA, Lehman JS, Koster MJ, Cantwell HM, Alavi A, *et al.* Cutaneous involvement in VEXAS syndrome: clinical and histopathologic findings. *Int J Dermatol.* 2023;62(7):938-45. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijd.16635>
10. Kouranloo K, Ashley A, Zhao SS, Dey M. Pulmonary manifestations in VEXAS (vacuoles, E1 enzyme, X-linked, autoinflammatory, somatic) syndrome: a systematic review. *Rheumatol Int.* 2023;43(6):1023-32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00296-022-05266-2>
11. Poulter JA, Collins JC, Cargo C, De Tute RM, Evans P, Ospina Cardona D, *et al.* Novel somatic mutations in UBA1 as a cause of VEXAS syndrome. *Blood.* 2021 Jul 1;137(26):3676-81. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood.2020010286>
12. Vitale A, Caggiano V, Bimonte A, Caroni F, Tosi GM, Fabbiani A, *et al.* VEXAS syndrome: a new paradigm for adult-onset monogenic autoinflammatory diseases. *Intern Emerg Med.* 2023 Apr;18(3):711-722. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11739-023-03193-z>
13. Richard Conway. Ruxolitinib takes center stage for VEXAS syndrome. *Blood.* 2022;140(8):807-08. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood.2022017056>